

OXIDATION OF HYDROCARBONS IN THE VAPOUR PHASE. PART II. HYDROAROMATIC HYDROCARBONS.

BY J. K. CHOWDHURY AND M. A. SABOOR.

Though hydroaromatic hydrocarbons form an important link between aromatic and aliphatic series, their oxidation does not appear to have received much attention. Jordan (*J. Chem. Met. Soc. S. Africa*, 1932, **32**, 248) reported the formation of small amounts of acraldehyde in the vapour phase oxidation of *cyclohexane*, using manganese vanadate as the catalyst while Yokoyama (*Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1933, **8**, 71) obtained various aliphatic dicarboxylic acids by electrochemical oxidation of *cyclohexane* at low temperature. Tetrahydronaphthalene was oxidised in the vapour phase by Maxted (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1928, 47) and by Green (*ibid.*, 1932, 159T) who obtained good yields of phthalic anhydride and found traces of naphthalene in the oxidation product.

The arrangement described in Part I was used in the oxidation of these hydrocarbons. When the hydrocarbons or their oxidation products were very volatile, the carburettor temperature and the rate of air-flow had to be carefully regulated and the products were cooled with ice-water in two successive coolers and the receiver was covered with wire gauze to avoid any risk from explosion. The uncondensed gases were led through water in succession washers to ensure complete absorption.

Oxidation of cycloHexane.—The temperature of the catalyst bed was not raised much above 400° on account of the danger of ignition. The condensate was at first light yellow in colour but became cherry red on exposure to air and light, and had an acrolein-like penetrating odour. It responded to tests for aldehydes, acids, unsaturates and peroxides. Amongst aldehydes, acrolein and acetaldehyde and amongst acids, acetic and pyruvic acids were indentified. It may be noted that formic acid, formaldehyde, *cyclohexanol* and *cyclohexane* could not be detected. The gaseous products of oxidation contained large amounts of carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide. No hydrogen or hydrocarbon was found.

The individual substances in the oxidation product were identified as follows :

(i) *Acetaldehyde.*—The liquid condensate was distilled and the presence of acetaldehyde in the distillate was confirmed by (a) iodoform test, (b)

Nessler's solution and, (c) colour test with sodium nitroprusside and piperidine in alkaline solution.

(ii) *Acrolein* was detected as a volatile substance having unsaturation and reducing properties and irritating the eyes.

(iii) *Acetic acid*.—The distillate was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, decolourised with a little animal charcoal and the presence of acetic acid was confirmed by the cacodyl oxide test.

(iv) *Pyruvic acid*.—The presence of this acid was unexpected as it escaped the notice of other workers. Its presence in the sodium salts was established by the following tests: (a) iodoform test, (b) reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate, (c) oxidation by potassium permanganate (d) colour test with β -naphthol-sulphuric acid, (e) colour test with phloroglucinol-hydrochloric acid and (f) evolution of CO_2 by the action of hydrogen peroxide.

(v) *Peroxides*.—The presence of peroxides was suspected from a small explosion in the receiver and was indicated by the evolution of iodine from potassium iodide.

The aldehydes were quantitatively estimated by means of sodium bisulphite and are expressed in terms of equivalent iodine, acids by titration in terms of succinic acid and peroxides from the amount of iodine evolved and are expressed in terms of equivalent oxygen.

When tin vanadate was used as the catalyst, the oxidation began at about 200° but at too high a temperature, *i. e.*, above 400° it tended to burn, sometimes with a flame and formed large quantities of carbon dioxide and monoxide, the ultimate products of oxidation. Even at moderate temperature only small amounts of intermediate compounds were obtained, a large portion being completely burnt off. If *cyclohexane* be passed through the reaction tube, either empty or filled with pumice only, no intermediate product was obtained in appreciable yield, but the introduction of tin vanadate improved the yield of intermediate products and lowered the temperature of reaction. Careful regulation of temperature and introduction of large quantities of air were found to have great influence on the nature and yield of the intermediate products. The curves I, II, and III (Fig. 1) will show how the yield of acids increased with the increase in air supply, the maximum yield being 4% acids (calculated as succinic acid) at a temperature of 310° . Excess of air disseminated the heat of reaction and thus improved the yield of acids. The higher rate of flow of air also shortened the time of contact and thus prevented complete oxidation. It was found that moderate temperatures (250° - 340°) favoured the formation of acids and peroxides, while higher temperatures

FIG. 1a

(350°-420°) favoured the formation of aldehydes and unsaturates, the carburettor temperature remaining constant at 25°. This may be due to (1) decomposition of the peroxides at a higher temperature producing aldehydes and (2) preferential combustion of hydrogen in comparison to carbon of the hydrocarbons, thus producing unsaturates.

The peroxide content of the product remained unchanged for about 24 hours but slowly changed on prolonged standing with increase of aldehydes, while the acids remained practically unchanged. The figures in Table I indicate changes in the composition of three separate samples on

allowing them to stand in air for three weeks. The increase in aldehyde content may be explained by the decomposition of peroxides of unsaturated hydrocarbons.

TABLE I.

	Sample I.		Sample II.		Sample III.	
	Initial.	Final.	Initial.	Final.	Initial.	Final.
Acids	0.0803	0.0875	0.3259	0.3259	0.2006	0.2019
Aldehydes	0.4666	0.5456	0.2857	0.2903	0.3220	0.3401
Peroxides	0.0866	0.0394	0.0930	0.0462	0.0775	0.0370

Oxidation of Decahydronaphthalene.

The decalin used in these investigations was purified by distillation before use. The general arrangement was the same as in the previous cases and tin vanadate supported on asbestos was mostly used as the catalyst. As in the previous cases, a large excess of air was necessary to dissipate the heat of reaction. The following substances were found in the product of oxidation: phthalic anhydride, maleic anhydride, succinic acid, naphthaquinone, formaldehyde, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide.

In order to obtain the maximum yield, various conditions such as quantity of air used, the rate of flow, temperature, etc. were varied and a maximum yield of 37.48% phthalic acid was obtained under the following conditions:

Diam. of the reaction tube, 1.5 cm.

Time of contact, 0.32 sec.

Catalyst space, 12 c.c.

Catalyst temp., 320°.

Air ratio, 3 times of the theoretical

Carburettor temp., 80°.

Thus it will be seen that under approximately the same conditions but with varying temperatures, the maximum yield of phthalic acid obtained from naphthalene, phenanthrene and decalin are 60.01%, 22.35% and 37.48% respectively, the yield being intermediate in the case of decalin. This is to be expected not only from the molecular structure of the three hydrocarbons in relation to phthalic acid but also from their heat of reaction which along

with the high temperature necessary in case of phenanthrene makes the control of the process very difficult.

Mechanism of Oxidation.—The oxidation of these hydrocarbons appears to follow a somewhat different course from the oxidation of aromatic hydrocarbons. The intermediate products obtained from *cyclohexane* are unsaturates, peroxides, acraldehyde, pyruvic acid, acetaldehyde and acetic acid while any cyclic alcohol or ketone or formaldehyde could not be identified. This may be represented by the following scheme :—

As benzene and its usual oxidation products could not be found, it is assumed that the oxidation does not appreciably proceed through benzene and maleic acid.

In the case of decalin, the following products were identified.—phthalic acid, maleic acid, succinic acid, benzoic acid (traces), 1:4-naphthaquinone and formaldehyde. Their formation may be explained by the following scheme :—

CHEMICAL LABORATORY
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received July 22, 1937.

